

Report on the assessment of the European potential SOC-sequestration

EJP SOIL - CarboSeq Deliverables WP9.2 and WP9.6 APPENDIX

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Documentation about the national simulations

Documentation on national simulations

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ESTONIA

Model toolbox input data preparation

ESTONIA

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i) Creation of the crop sequence:

1. The maps from the Agricultural Registers and Information Board (PRIA) for the period 2016-2022 were used to collect the main crop for each field for this period. The total number of fields was 175976, with a total surface of 973637 ha.
2. The crop sequence for the period 2016-2022 was cloned to generate a sequence of 20 years. The missing data was filled with the mode of the series for the field, if missing with the mode of crop, and if missing with the mode of the whole dataset.

As the field ID is unique for each year, the fields were joined for different years by location considering the largest overlap. The ID for 2022 is used as reference.

3. The average SOC and clay value was calculated for each field from national SOC and clay maps (references).

ii) Data of manure production was calculated using two files:

4. The animal census was obtained from state statistical office public databases: https://andmed.stat.ee/en/stat/majandus_pellumajandus_pellumajandussaaduste-tootmine_loomakasvatussaaduste-tootmine/PM09
5. The total C in manure production by County was calculated as:

TC manure/year <- total number of animals * t manure/year*animal * %DM * %C_in_DM

iii) Crop data

6. Data of yield per crop, year and County was obtained from the state statistical office public databases:

https://andmed.stat.ee/et/stat/majandus_pellumajandus_pellumajandussaaduste-tootmine_taimekasvatussaaduste-tootmine/PM0281

7. A separate file was created with reference 'sowing date', 'harvest date' and 'prop_residue_removal' for each crop for Estonia.

iv) Data combination

8. Crop parameters (data from nr.7) was joined then by crop.
9. Manure C addition was joined by County.
10. Yield from PM0281 (file created in point nr.12) was joined by csopra category, year and maakond.

v) Joining crop and soil data with grid (10x10km grid)

11. Soil and Crop data are joined and summarised according to the 10x10km grid, with a new ID for each cell. The crop sequence is created by assigning proportionally to

the 20-year crop sequence for the cell, the frequency of the crops in the fields during the full period).

vi) Running the model

12. The data was used to run the model in <https://coby.infosol.inrae.fr:8080/>

vii) Postprocessing and plotting

13. The obtained modeled SOC was summarized and plotted.

Results discussion

ESTONIA

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The results from the modeling for the BAU scenario were different from the results of previous modeling exercises we have carried out for Estonia (EERC Report, 2022; FAO, 2022). The SOC loss for the period was approximately double of the SOC loss estimated in previous scenarios (17% vs. 8%). At the moment, we cannot pinpoint the exact cause of this difference. We would advise not to focus on the final absolute values of SOC and SOC change, but rather on the differences between scenarios.

In our opinion, the differences in final SOC change of the different scenarios compared to BAU are logical for the Estonian conditions.

- “Biochar”, as expected increased the final value of SOC significantly (a 28.3% compared to BAU).
- The “More cover” (COVERMORE) scenario also increased the final SOC (an 8.9% compared to BAU), reducing the SOC loss.
- The “Ley” scenario and the “All straw left in the field” (STRAWALL), both resulted in neglectable increases of SOC compared to the BAU scenario (< 1% for both).
- The “No cover” (COVERNO) and the “All straw removed” (STRAWNO) scenarios both resulted in bigger SOC losses than BAU, but the differences were small (- 3.0% and -1.0%, respectively).

The small effect of some of the treatments is due to the predominance of Grassland area in Estonia (a predominance that was increased when summarising the crop sequence of the different fields to create the crop sequence of the 10x10km grid cells, and also by the gap-filling of the crop sequence for some fields using the mode). This explains why scenarios like “Ley” and those regarding cereal residues (“No straw removed” and “All straw removed”) has such a neglectable effect.

Results

Initial SOC: 101.1624 (t ha⁻¹)

Scenario	Final SOC (t ha⁻¹)	SOC Change (t ha⁻¹)	SOC Change (%)
BAU	83.21239	-17.950052	-17.678925
BIOCHAR	105.45842	4.295969	5.419698
COVERMORE	89.46269	-11.699760	-11.220679

Scenario	Final SOC (t ha-1)	SOC Change (t ha-1)	SOC Change (%)
COVERNO	80.62536	-20.537083	-20.267264
LEY	83.21325	-17.949193	-17.677962
STRAWALL	83.48477	-17.677675	-17.391604
STRAWNO	82.39149	-18.770961	-18.545283

Scenario	Final SOC compared to BAU (tC/ha)	Final SOC compared to BAU (%)
BAU	0.0000000	0.0000000
BIOCHAR	22.2460212	28.3016847
COVERMORE	6.2502918	7.9303793
COVERNO	-2.5870312	-3.0925065
LEY	0.0008588	0.0011753
STRAWALL	0.2723773	0.3526065
STRAWNO	-0.8209086	-1.0630936

References

EERC Report 2022: Assessment of Changes in Soil Organic Carbon Stocks on Agricultural Land with Mineral Soils Using a Simulation Model. 2022. Commissioned by: Estonian Environmental Research Centre (EERC). Conducted by: Estonian University of Life Sciences.

FAO (2022). The Global Soil Organic Carbon Sequestration Potential Map. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. <https://data.apps.fao.org/glois/?lang=en>

GERMANY

EJP Soil / CarboSeq

German national runs with the Model Toolbox

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1. Introduction

Agricultural soils can be both a source and a sink of carbon from the atmosphere. Agricultural management can help to increase soil organic carbon stocks. To promote carbon-friendly management, carbon farming schemes were created that aim at returning money to the farmers for increasing SOC stocks. Models pose a chance for estimating the SOC change cost-efficiently, but there is large uncertainty of different modelling approaches (Riggers et al., 2019).

In the CarboSeq project from the EJP Soil program, our aim is to model a feasible potential to increase SOC stocks of European arable land via various management options. Modelling is done in a harmonized way using the same methodological approach and the best management data available for each country.

This study aims at (1) modelling the SOC sequestration potential for German croplands using this harmonized approach from the model toolbox, and (2) to quantify the uncertainty of the C input estimation method and how the chosen method determines the estimated sequestration potential and climate mitigation effects.

2. Material and Methods

a. Data

We used soil and management data from the first German Agricultural Soil Inventory (Jacobs et al., 2020; Poeplau et al., 2020). In brief, over 3000 agricultural soils in Germany were sampled and analyzed. We selected mineral soils without water-logging (groundwater level > 80cm below the surface) and under arable land-use with at least 3 years of recorded management. This resulted in a data-set with 1819 sites.

b. Scenarios

In total, 6 scenarios were run to estimate the SOC accrual potential of 4 SOC sequestration measures (Ley rotations, Biochar application, Cover crops and Crop residues) compared to a business-as-usual scenario.

For the business-as-usual scenario, we looped recent management data obtained from the first German Agricultural Soil Inventory (Jacobs et al., 2020) over 20 years and combined them with sowing and harvest dates obtained from regional agricultural advisory services.

In the ley rotation scenario, we replaced all silage maize from the BAU scenario with leys (13% of all cultivation years). We kept the same sowing and harvest dates and recent cover crops, and assumed an average yield of 32.6 t FM ha⁻¹ based on yield information from the business-as-usual scenario (see appendix).

In the biochar scenario, we assumed an annual biochar application of 1.87 t C ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ over 20 years on sites where the soil pH (water) was ≤ 7 (63% of all sites). This application rate corresponds to a total application of 50 t Biochar ha⁻¹ (37.4 t C ha⁻¹).

For cover crops, we ran two scenarios: In the “potential cover crop” scenario, we assumed additional cover crops in cultivation windows between main crops (1) harvested before October and (2) sown after March as described in Seitz et al. (2023), which increased the annual cover cropping area from

10% to 29%. In the “no cover crop” scenario, we removed all cover crops from the crop rotations (0% cover cropping area). Each cover crop is associated with a default C input of 3.11 t C ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ as implemented in the model toolbox.

For the residues, we ran a “no residues” scenario, where the parameter *prop_residues_removal* was set to 1 for all straw crops (oats, summer barley, winter barley, winter rye, winter triticale, and winter wheat) which means that all residues from straw crops are removed from the field. In total, 60% of all residues are removed in this scenario (compared to 26% in the BAU scenario). No “potential residues” scenario was run since in Germany, there are no residues burned in the field. Thus, there is no potential to use residues for additional SOC accrual in Germany.

Table 1: Overview over all scenarios, assumptions and which allometric approaches were run for each scenario.

Scenario	Assumption	Allometric approaches
Business-as-usual	Management data obtained from the first German Agricultural Soil Inventory via farmer questionnaires (Jacobs et al., 2020)	Bol Bze Ccb Ctool Ipc
Potential ley	1. Replace all silage maize with leys (13% of all cultivation years) 2. Assumed yield: 32.6 t FM ha ⁻¹ 3. No residues removed 4. Dates, cover crops and fertilizer stay the same	Bol Bze Ccb Ctool Ipc
Potential biochar	Annual biochar application of 1.87 t C ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹ over 20 years on sites where the soil pH (water) was ≤ 7 (65% of all sites)	Bol Ccb Ipc
No cover crop	No cover crops	Bol Ccb Ipc
Potential cover crop	Additional cover crops in cultivation windows between main crops (1) harvested before October and (2) sown after March (29% of all management years)	Bol Ccb Ipc
No residues	All residues from straw crops (oats, summer barley, winter barley, winter rye, winter triticale, and winter wheat) are removed (60% vs. 26% in the BAU scenario)	Bol Ccb Ipc
Potential residues	Not applicable in Germany	

c. Models and C input estimation methods

We used the 5-pool SOC decomposition model RothC (Coleman & Jenkinson, 1996).

For the BAU scenario and the ley scenario, we tested 5 carbon input estimation methods and the effect on estimated sequestration potentials: *bolinder* (Bolinder et al., 2007), *bze/weiser* (Jacobs et al., 2020), *ccb/franko* (Franko et al., 2011), *ctool* (Taghizadeh-Toosi et al., 2014) and *ipcc* (Rösemann et al., 2017).

For all other sequestration scenarios, we tested 3 methods: *bolinder* (Bolinder et al., 2007), *ccb/franko* (Franko et al., 2011) and *ipcc* (Rösemann et al., 2017).

d. Software and Statistics

We used the model toolbox (Martin et al. in prep) implemented in R Version 4.4.2 (R Core Team, 2024) which uses the RothC implementation of the SoilR package (Sierra et al., 2012) to run the simulations. The C input estimation methods were implemented in C++ in the C inest module (Riggers et al., 2019) which is part of the model toolbox. The model toolbox sampled monthly weather data for the years 2000-2020 from the AgERA5 data set (Boogaard et al., 2020) based on coordinates.

e. Analysis

Based on the modelled SOC stock dynamics, we calculated relative and absolute SOC changes compared to (1) the initial SOC stock, and (2) the SOC dynamic of the business-as-usual scenario modelled with the same allometric function.

Some crop rotations were stretched to up to 30 years by the model toolbox, probably due to overlapping harvest and sowing dates. We were not able to solve this problem due to the limited time available. The plots show the mean SOC dynamic over 20 years, but the relative and absolute SOC changes given in the tables were calculated for the average SOC stock of the last 12 months for each site.

Emission factors (EF) were calculated only for those sites, where the measure was implemented, using the following equation 1:

$$EF = \frac{SOC_{measure}}{SOC_{BAU}}$$

3. Results

a. Business-as-usual scenario

Figure 1: Relative soil organic carbon stock changes in the business-as-usual scenario over time, estimated with 5 different C input estimation methods and relative to the initial SOC stock. Dark grey lines represent site variability and show SOC dynamics of single sites modelled with the default method (bolinder). Thick coloured lines represent the mean of all sites modelled with each of the 5 different allometric approaches.

In the business-as-usual scenario, the mean modelled change in SOC stocks ranged between -0.32 (-8.9% , *ipcc*) and $+0.13$ $t\ C\ ha^{-1}\ a^{-1}$ ($+8.6\%$, *bolinder*) (Figure 1, Table 2). In total, 3 out of 5 C input estimation methods predicted decreasing SOC stocks.

Table 2: Averaged SOC change (relative and absolute) per C input estimation method. The baseline here is the measured SOC stock (SOC at $t=2000$).

Method	Relative SOC change	Absolute SOC change	Annual SOC change
unit	%	$t\ C\ ha^{-1}$	$t\ C\ ha^{-1}\ a^{-1}$
reference	$SOC_{(t=2000)}$	$SOC_{(t=2000)}$	$SOC_{(t=2000)}$
Bolinder	8.6%	2.7	0.13
BZE / Weiser	-0.9%	-2.2	-0.11
CCB / Franko	-5.0%	-4.4	-0.22
ctool	4.5%	0.5	0.02
IPCC	-8.9%	-6.5	-0.32

b. Potential ley scenario

Figure 2: Relative SOC change of implementing ley over time modelled with 5 different C input estimation methods and compared to the BAU scenario.

Replacing silage maize with ley in the ley scenario resulted in an average modelled SOC change between -0.01 (*ipcc*) and $+0.09$ (*BZE/Weiser*) $t C ha^{-1} a^{-1}$ on all modelled sites and compared to the BAU scenario (Figure 2, Table 3). This corresponds to an emission factor between 0.99 and 1.08 on sites where the measure was implemented (13% of all management years).

Table 3: Emission factor and modelled effect of ley on soil organic carbon varies with the C input estimation method used. The baseline here is the business-as-usual scenario modelled with the corresponding C input estimation method.

	Relative SOC change	Emission factor	Absolute SOC change	Annual SOC change	Annual SOC change	Annual SOC change
<i>unit</i>	-	-	$t C ha^{-1}$	$t C ha^{-1} a^{-1}$	<i>permille</i>	$t C ha^{-1} a^{-1}$
<i>reference</i>	All sites, SOC_{BAU}	Ley sites, SOC_{BAU}	All sites, SOC_{BAU}	All sites, SOC_{BAU}	SOC_{BAU}	All sites, $SOC_{(t=2000)}$
Bolinder	-0.1%	1.00	-0.11	-0.01	-0.09	0.13
BZE / Weiser	3.6%	1.08	1.88	0.09	1.57	-0.02
CCB / Franko	1.2%	1.03	0.61	0.03	0.50	-0.19
ctool	2.4%	1.05	1.27	0.06	1.06	0.09
IPCC	-0.3%	0.99	-0.16	-0.01	-0.13	-0.33

c. Potential biochar scenario

Figure 3: Relative SOC change with biochar application over time modelled with 3 different C input estimation methods and compared to the BAU scenario.

The biochar scenario showed a large SOC increase between 42% (*bolinder*) and 50% (*ipcc*) compared to the BAU scenario. Mean absolute SOC change was the same for all allometric approaches, with $22.79 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ on all sites and $34.7 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ on biochar sites (65% of all sites).

Table 4: Emission factor and modelled effect of biochar on soil organic carbon varies with the C input estimation method used. The baseline here is the business-as-usual scenario modelled with the corresponding C input estimation method.

	Relative SOC change	Emission factor	Absolute SOC change	Annual SOC change	Annual SOC change	Annual SOC change
<i>unit</i>	-	-	t C ha^{-1}	$\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$	permille	$\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$
<i>reference</i>	All sites, SOC_{BAU}	Biochar sites, SOC_{BAU}	All sites, SOC_{BAU}	All sites, SOC_{BAU}	SOC_{BAU}	All sites, $\text{SOC}_{(t=2000)}$
Bolinder	42.4%	1.65	22.79	1.14	19	1.27
CCB / Franko	47.7%	1.73	22.79	1.14	19	0.92
IPCC	50.0%	1.76	22.79	1.14	19	0.82

d. No residue scenario

Figure 4: Relative SOC change over time when all residues from straw crops are removed from the field, modelled with 3 different C input estimation methods and compared to the BAU scenario.

In the no-residues scenario, SOC stocks decreased by -9.2% (*bolinder*) to -4.5% (*ipcc*) on average, which corresponds to an annual SOC change of -0.29 to -0.11 t C ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ compared to the BAU scenario.

Table 5: Emission factor and modelled effect of residue removal on soil organic carbon varies with the C input estimation method used. The baseline here is the business-as-usual scenario modelled with the corresponding C input estimation method.

	Relative SOC change	Emission factor	Absolute SOC change	Annual SOC change	Annual SOC change	Annual SOC change
unit	-	-	t C ha ⁻¹	t C ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	permille	t C ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹
reference	All sites, SOC _{BAU}	No-resid sites, SOC _{BAU}	SOC _{BAU}	SOC _{BAU}	SOC _{BAU}	SOC _(t=2000)
Bolinder	-9.2%	0.88	-5.78	-0.29	-4.8	-0.16
CCB / Franko	-6.8%	0.91	-3.62	-0.18	-3.0	-0.40
IPCC	-4.5%	0.94	-2.30	-0.11	-1.9	-0.44

e. No cover crop scenario

Figure 5: Relative SOC change over time when all cover crops are removed, modelled with 3 different C input estimation methods for main crops and compared to the BAU scenario.

In the no cover crop scenario, SOC stocks decreased by -3.4% (*bolinder*) to -3.2% (*ipcc*) on average, corresponding to an annual SOC change of $-0.09 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ compared to the BAU scenario.

Table 6: Emission factor and modelled effect of removing cover crops on soil organic carbon varies with the C input estimation method used. The baseline here is the business-as-usual scenario modelled with the corresponding C input estimation method.

	Relative SOC change	Emission factor	Absolute SOC change	Annual SOC change	Annual SOC change	Annual SOC change
<i>unit</i>	-	-	t C ha^{-1}	$\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$	<i>permille</i>	$\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$
<i>reference</i>	All sites, SOC_{BAU}	No cover crop sites, SOC_{BAU}	SOC_{BAU}	SOC_{BAU}	SOC_{BAU}	$\text{SOC}_{(t=2000)}$
Bolinder	-3.2%	0.92	-1.90	-0.09	-1.6	0.04
CCB / Franko	-3.3%	0.92	-1.82	-0.09	-1.5	-0.31
IPCC	-3.4%	0.92	-1.80	-0.09	-1.5	-0.41

f. Potential cover crop scenario

Figure 6: Relative SOC change over time when all cover crops are removed, modelled with 3 different C input estimation methods for main crops and compared to the BAU scenario.

Adding cover crops in available cultivation windows resulted in an average modelled SOC increase between 0.18 (+7.3%, *ipcc*) and 0.19 (+6.7%, *bolinder*) $t C ha^{-1} a^{-1}$ on all modelled sites and compared to the BAU scenario (Figure 2, Table 3). This corresponds to an emission factor of 1.06 on sites where the measure was implemented (additional cover crops in 19% of all management years).

Table 7: Emission factor and modelled effect of removing cover crops on soil organic carbon varies with the C input estimation method used. The baseline here is the business-as-usual scenario modelled with the corresponding C input estimation method.

	Relative SOC change	Emission factor	Absolute SOC change	Annual SOC change	Annual SOC change	Annual SOC change
<i>unit</i>	-	-	$t C ha^{-1}$	$t C ha^{-1} a^{-1}$	<i>permille</i>	$t C ha^{-1} a^{-1}$
<i>reference</i>	All sites, SOC_{BAU}	Pot cover crop sites, SOC_{BAU}	SOC_{BAU}	SOC_{BAU}	SOC_{BAU}	$SOC_{(t=2000)}$
Bolinder	6.7%	1.06	3.75	0.19	3.1	0.32
CCB / Franko	7.1%	1.06	3.59	0.18	3.0	-0.04
IPCC	7.3%	1.06	3.54	0.18	2.9	-0.15

4. Discussion

a. Business-as-usual scenario

We found a large variation in SOC trends modelled with the 5 allometric approaches, similar to findings by (Riggers et al., 2019). The largest increase of SOC stocks was modelled with the *bolinder* approach, which is the default allometric approach of the Model toolbox used by the other project partners. However, other studies have shown a decreasing trend for German arable SOC stocks of $-0.2 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ (Riggers et al., 2021; Seitz et al., 2023). This SOC stock change rate is similar to the one resulting from *ccb* approach used in this study ($-0.22 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$), so I conclude that the *ccb* approach delivers more accurate results for German croplands compared to the default *bolinder* approach.

b. Sequestration scenarios

i. Ley

Our modelled emission factors for ley ranged between 0.99 (*ipcc*) and 1.08 (*bze/weiser*). These estimates are similar to emission factors that were found for forage legumes on 23 European long-term field experiments, ranging between 1.02 and 1.22 for a reference SOC stock of 60 t C ha^{-1} (depending on the increase of legumes in the rotation) (Panagea et al., submitted; Ruyschaert et al., 2023).

The effect of ley showed large variations over the 5 C input estimation methods: The C input is sometimes strongly correlated with the given yield (*bolinder*), and sometimes it is constant (*ccb/franko*). For 2 out of 5 allometric approaches (*bolinder* and *ipcc*), the simulations resulted in decreasing SOC stocks. This can be explained by the fact that in these approaches, silage maize delivered more C input than leys for the given high yields (see Table 8, Figure 9 in Appendix). This shows that these approaches are not suitable for modelling the SOC accrual effect of leys, which has been found in long-term field experiments (Panagea et al., submitted; Ruyschaert et al., 2023). It is therefore recommended to use the approaches *ctool*, *bze/weiser* or *ccb/franko* for this scenario.

ii. Biochar

Biochar addition resulted in the highest SOC increase of $1.14 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ on average. This is caused by the exceptionally high application rate of $1.87 \text{ t Biochar-C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ on 65% of the sites over 20 years. This scenario is not feasible since a large amount of biomass is needed to create the biochar: “68 years would be needed to produce the maximum potential biochar amount suggested for this measure” as stated in the WP8 report. Thus, it is not really comparable to the other measures in terms of feasibility.

iii. No straw residues and no cover crops

Removing all straw residues from the fields resulted in higher SOC losses than removing all cover crops from the fields (-4% to -9% vs. -3%, respectively). For maintaining current levels of SOC stocks it is thus very important to keep straw residues and cover crops on the field.

The SOC effect of recent cover crops (BAU compared to no cover crops) is higher than what was found in a similar study with the same data (Seitz et al., 2023) ($0.09 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ vs. $0.04 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$, respectively). This can be explained by the higher C input that was assumed to be $3.1 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ as implemented in the model toolbox. In contrast, Seitz et al. (2023) assumed a lower cover crop induced C input ranging on average between 1.7 and $2.6 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ depending on the sowing date, temperature and precipitation.

iv. Cover crops

The emission factor calculated for the potential cover crops scenario was 1.06, which is exactly the same as was found for European long-term field experiments in CarboSeq-WP2 (Ruysschaert et al., 2023).

In a similar study, Seitz et al. (2023) found an annual SOC increase of $0.09 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ over 20 years (ambitious implementation of cover crops compared to a BAU scenario). The annual SOC change of $0.18 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ over 20 years modelled with the model toolbox is higher which can be explained by the higher C input that was assumed to be $3.1 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$. In contrast, Seitz et al. (2023) assumed a lower cover crop induced C input ranging on average between 1.7 and $2.6 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ depending on the sowing date, temperature and precipitation.

5. Conclusion

Implementing additional cover crops has a higher potential for SOC accrual than implementing leys ($0.18 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ vs. $0.03\text{-}0.09 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$). This can be explained by the larger area of implementation on 19% of all management years for additional cover crops vs. 13% of all management years for additional leys, but also by the higher emission factor in most cases. The highest SOC accrual potential of $1.14 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ (19 permille!) on average was found for biochar in a less feasible scenario with a high biochar application rate of $1.87 \text{ t Biochar-C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ on 65% of all sites.

Removing straw residues and recent cover crops from current crop rotations would result in SOC losses of -0.11 to $-0.29 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ and $-0.09 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$, respectively. It is therefore very important to maintain current management practices that deliver C input to arable soils.

6. Appendix

a. Yield of ley crops in the BZE data-set

Figure 7: Density plots of ley yield in the BZE data-set. Green (=1) is estimated, red (=0) is reported by farmers.

Table 8: How the C input varies with the C input estimation method for the same yield-crop combination.

Cines t ID	Crop type	Yield t FM/D $M ha^{-1}$ a^{-1}	xmow	Mowing frequency	C input $t C ha^{-1} a^{-1}$				
					Bolind er	BZE / Weiser	CCB / Franko	ctool	ipcc
1	Silage maize	44.5 +- 11.0	n.d.	n.d.	3.19+- 0.79	1.58+- 0.39	1.91+- 0.09	2.97+- 0.59	1.18+ -0.29
74	Ley / grass- clover	32.6	0.330	3	2.38	5.39	3.07	4.89	1.19
93	grass	32.6	0.330	3	2.97	2.3	3.19	3.82	1.31

Bolinder

Franko

Figure 8: C input over yield for 2 C input estimation methods (left: Bolinder, right: Franko).

7. References

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HUNGARY

National run in Carboseq project

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Determining the representative points

For model simulation the input files were created on a 10x10 km grid for Hungary. In all grid a representative simulation point was detected. To determine the representative points, we used the raster cells selected by Fodor et al. (2021). The grid was aligned to the 0.1°×0.1° resolution (approximately 10×10 km) regular grid that is defined by CARPATCLIM database (Spinoni et al. 2015). The points were selected based on the primary soil properties of the DOSoReMI database (Pásztor et al. 2020; sand-, silt-, clay-, and soil organic matter content, bulk density), and the EU-SoilHydroGrids 3D soil hydrology database (Tóth et al. 2017).

Altogether 1104 representative points were determined for Hungary.

Creating soil file

Clay content for the topsoil (0-30 cm, %) of Hungary were extracted from the DOSoReMI database (Pásztor et al. 2020) at the representative points. Soil organic carbon (SOC) stock for the topsoil (0–30 cm, tons/ha) of Hungary for the year 2000 were extracted from the database of Szatmári et al. (2024) at the representative points.

Creating crop file

The crop files were compiled using the cultivation data of the National Statistical Office, available by county. In Hungary there are 19 counties in total, with Budapest data separately, so altogether there are separate data for 20 regions. The main crops grown per region were identified and the proportion of land use was compiled to determine the number of crops in the rotation over the 20 years. Crops that occurred at least on 5% of the area were shown in the crop rotation, with 5% of the area representing one year. For each representative points, we have defined the soil category of the point, which was classified according to the national soil-type map for Hungary (Pásztor et al. 2018) of the DOSoReMI database. The categories are defined based on the Hungarian Soil Classification System as follows:

- Chernozems
- Brown forest soils
- Meadow- and alluvial soils
- Sand soils
- Salt-affected soils
- Shallow soils

These soil categories were taken into account in creating of the crop rotation. It is ensured that a higher proportion of maize, for example, was present on better quality soils.

In total, 8 plants were added to the rotation.

As there is no precise geographical information on the spatial distribution of cover crops - we only know that cover crops are grown on about 2% of the arable land in Hungary we have

displayed this measure on 2% of the representative points each year. In randomly selecting the points, we took into account the need to place cover crops before of spring-sown crops. Typically, cover crops are grown between fall-harvested crops and spring-sown crops in our country due to climatic conditions.

The extent of biochar application is not available in the national database, but may in fact be negligible, so this measure is not included in the baseline scenario crop file. Data on the use of cattle manure and pig slurry were available in the national database. By region, there was data on the area and amount of manure applied per year in the region. This was used to determine how many representative points in each region should be used to represent manure application, using the region data as the amount applied. Since there was no accurate data on the geographic location of the areas where manure was applied, points were chosen that were close to large cattle or pig farms. The same approach was used to define the irrigated areas, where the average amount of irrigation water applied and the irrigated area per region per year were available. The points representing irrigated areas were selected near water abstraction points (reservoirs, rivers). The yield data of the crops grown per region are available for all years, and these were used in the crop file.

Scenarios

We ran a total of 6 scenarios, based on the guide.

- Baseline: The crop file was created as described above.
- No cover crop: In this scenario, the cover crop was removed at all representative points, other parameter remained unchanged.
- Pot cover crop: In this scenario we put cover crops into the rotation in those years when winter wheat is followed by spring-sown *Heianthus annuus* and GrainCorn. This brought the total to 29.6% of cover crops.
- No residue: In this scenario, we took all the residue from all cereals according to the instructions.
- Pot residue: In this scenario, we left all the residue in all cereals according to the instructions.
- Pot ley. In this scenario, we have replaced the silage maize with legume according to the instructions.

Results

Since cover crops are sown only on 2% of the areas, the baseline scenario and the nocovercrop scenario did not differ significantly. The same is true for the potley scenario, as only one of the 20 regions in Hungary grows silage maize in an area share of more than 5 %. So, these three scenarios are no different from each other. The no residues scenario increased the national average SOC loss by about 1.5 times, while the best result was achieved with the pot cover crop scenario, where carbon loss is reduced to 17% of the value in the baseline.

During the model run, the delta SOC was determined for each representative point over the 20-year period (2000-2019) for all scenarios using the built-in commands in the Model Tool Box. By averaging the delta SOC values obtained at each representative point, the national average SOC change for each scenario was also determined. Similarly, for each point, for each scenario, we determined the initial and final SOC content, which is required for the map visualization.

These data can be found in the “**delta SOC**” file on three different work sheets (initial and final SOC_in all ID, deltaSOC_in all ID, delta SOC_national).

We have also determined the national average SOC content for each scenario for each year, these data can be found in the “**SOC_national**” file.

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PORTUGAL

Summary report of CarboSeq *ModelToolBox* national runs for Portugal

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Modelling approach

We adopted a region-based modelling approach due to limitations in data availability and resources available during the time for completing the task. This approach used crop, yield, and management data from national agricultural statistics. Five modelled regions, corresponding to the Portuguese mainland NUTS II units from 2013¹, were modelled. Each NUTS II was treated as a simulation unit (ID) in *ModelToolBox*.

Developing the Crop Data File (crop.csv)

Crop area data from national agricultural statistics for the 2013 NUTS II classification were used, covering years 2023, 2019, 2016, 2013, and 2009. Only temporary crops were included in the simulations. The 20-years crop rotation for each region (ID) was created as follows:

- 1) **Crop identification:** temporary crops were included in the rotation if occupied over 3% of crop area in at least one of the years.
- 2) **Rotation:** the frequency of each crop in the 20-years the rotation was calculated based on its average area fraction across the five reference years.
- 3) **Order of the crops:** The crops were arranged in sequences to avoid inconsistencies in the start and end dates when winter and spring crops occur in the rotation.

When statistics were not detailed enough to identify crop types, specific assumptions were made. A list of these assumptions is shown in Table 1. The list of sources and assumption used for the other variables in the Crop Data File are listed in Table 2.

Table 1. Crop type as named in the national statistics and corresponding *csopra* ontology. The table shows only cases where a direct translation was not possible and assumptions had to be made.

Temporary crop national in statistics	Modeltoolbox ²
"Temporary grassland"	GrassWithoutLegume
"Forage oats"	AvenaSativa
"Other legumes"	ViciaFaba
"Horticultural crops"	BrassicaOleraceaVar.Sabauda
"Annual consociations"	BrassicaOleraceaVar.Sabauda
"Other forage crop"	Not modelled ³ (in practice it could be very different things legumes/cereals)
"Rice"	Not modelled (not in <i>csopra</i> ontology)
"Ornamental flowers"	Not modelled (not in <i>csopra</i> ontology)

¹ There was a change in the NUTS II in 2024, but mots statistics are not available for these new units.

² From <https://csopra.pages.mia.inra.fr/OWLifier/concepts.html>

³ In these cases, the 20 years were divided by the other crops in the region (according to the criteria in described in 1), 2), and 3)).

Table 2. Assumptions and sources for data used in the Crop Data File (crop.csv).

Data	Assumptions	Source
Crop	Years existing: 2023, 2019, 2026, 1013, and 2009. Included in the rotation if >3% in any year. Number of years in rotation proportional to the area in the 5 years average.	https://www.ine.pt/xportal/xmain?xpid=INE&xpgid=ine_indicadores&indOcorrCod=0005638&contexto=bd&selTab=tab2&xlang=en
Yield	Average for all years between 2009 and 2022.	https://www.ine.pt/xportal/xmain?xpid=INE&xpgid=ine_indicadores&indOcorrCod=0000022&contexto=bd&selTab=tab2&xlang=en
Irrigation and irrigation amount	Irrigation was chosen according to statistics for 2019. Irrigation amounts were taken from recent statistics which exist only for 2023.	https://www.ine.pt/xportal/xmain?xpid=INE&xpgid=ine_indicadores&indOcorrCod=0010599&contexto=bd&selTab=tab2&xlang=en https://www.ine.pt/xportal/xmain?xpid=INE&xpgid=ine_indicadores&indOcorrCod=0013726&contexto=bd&selTab=tab2&xlang=en
Exogenous organic matter	Statistics for 2019 indicate the percentage of cropland which apply exogenous organic matter. Amounts and types were estimated according to practice.	https://www.ine.pt/xportal/xmain?xpid=INE&xpgid=ine_indicadores&indOcorrCod=0010594&contexto=bd&selTab=tab2&xlang=en
Cover crops	All crops harvested before the end of April (typically horticultural crops) had a following cover crop, as well as silage and grain corn, which is harvested in August/September and sown again in March. This is the general practice in Portugal. Crops harvested after Spring are all rainfed winter crops, therefore, it is assumed that a rainfed cover crop is not possible in Spring/Summer.	
Residues removal	Residue removal of 0.9 was assumed for forage crops and 0.5 for grain crops.	

Modelled scenarios

The scenarios were chosen according to the common guidelines developed for national runs:

- A. Baseline – this scenario used cover crops and residue removal according to description in Table 2.
- B. No residues – all residues in cereal crops were removed.
- C. Potential residues - all residues in cereal crops were kept in the field.
- D. No cover crop – no cover crops were considered in the rotation.
- E. Potential cover crop (same as baseline) – because the baseline is already considering all feasible cover crops, this is the same as A.
- F. Potential ley – all “SilageCorn” was replaced with “LegumeMixture”.
- G. Potential biochar – 1,87 tC/ha/year were considered in regions 1 and 4, where pH was below 7.

Developing the Soil Data File (soil.csv)

Information for location and soil was selected from the soil database *Infosolo*⁴, by choosing a location for cropland in each region in which the reference 20-year rotation was applicable. This approach was thought to be more realistic than to perform statistics over the cropland soils occurring in the regions. The coordinates and soil properties are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Coordinates and soil properties used in the Soil Data File.

ID	NUT II	LAT	LON	CLAY	SILT	OC_THA	pH	CaCO3
1	Norte	41.08418	-7.78113	7	9	90	5.6	0
2	Centro	39.5069	-8.60226	14	6.2	45	6.9	0
3	Lisboa e Vale do Tejo	39.0305	-9.310355	12.5	12.9	45	7	0
4	Alentejo	38.01173	-8.20246	8	3.2	20	5.4	0
5	Algarve	37.15574	-8.22578	31	23	45	8	0

Visualization of the results

Figures 1 – 5 show the changes during the 20-year rotation in the different scenarios for ID 1 to 5.

⁴ <https://projects.inia.pt/infosolo/>

Figure 1. SOC (t/ha) changes during the 20-year rotation for ID 1 (Norte) in the different scenarios.

Figure 2. SOC (t/ha) changes during the 20-year rotation for ID 2 (Centro) in the different scenarios. Note that biochar is not applied in this region due to the high soil pH.

Figure 3. SOC (t/ha) changes during the 20-year rotation for ID 3 (Lisboa), in the different scenarios. Note that biochar is not applied in this region due to high soil pH.

Figure 4. SOC (t/ha) changes during the 20-year rotation for ID 4 (Alentejo), in the different scenarios.

Figure 5. SOC (t/ha) changes during the 20-year rotation for ID 5 (Algarve), in the different scenarios. Note that biochar is not applied in this region due to high soil pH. Note that the “Ley” scenario is the same as the “Baseline” because there is no forage corn in the region.

The total Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) in the 30 cm of soil, can be calculated using the area of temporary crops area considered in each ID, as shown in Table 4. Table 5 and Figure 5 show the total SOC in the simulated area, for each ID and in total.

Table 4. Area of temporary crops for each ID considered in the simulation.

ID	Temporary Crops area (average 2009-2023) [ha]	Temporary Crops area (2023) [ha]
1	127835	107786
2	158310	147636
3	27516	27014
4	430305	381322
5	10138	7509
Total	754104	671267

Table 5. Soil Organic Carbon (t) for the different simulated scenarios. SOC was calculated from *ModelToolBox* results at the end time of the simulation and the average temporary crop areas for the simulated period (Table 4).

ID	Baseline (t)	No residues (t)	Potential residues (t)	No cover crops (t)	Potential ley (t)	Biochar (t)
1	1.010E+07	9.955E+06	1.039E+07	8.329E+06	1.017E+07	1.461E+07
2	7.414E+06	7.201E+06	7.806E+06	5.572E+06	7.419E+06	7.414E+06
3	1.339E+06	1.314E+06	1.406E+06	8.794E+05	1.329E+06	1.339E+06
4	3.032E+05	2.935E+05	3.364E+05	1.674E+05	3.032E+05	6.555E+05

5	3.558E+07	3.489E+07	3.854E+07	2.684E+07	3.558E+07	3.558E+07
Total	5.474E+07	5.365E+07	5.848E+07	4.179E+07	5.481E+07	5.960E+07

Figure 6. Soil Organic Carbon (t) for the different simulated scenarios. SOC was calculated from *ModelToolBox* results at the end time of the simulation and the average temporary crop areas for the simulated period (Table 4).

Conclusions:

According to the simulation results, the baseline scenario for SOC in the area of temporary crops in Portugal stores 54,74 Mt of SOC. The “Biochar” shows, the highest potential for increase in SOC of 59,60 Mt, followed by “Potential residues” with 58,48 Mt, and “Ley” with 54,81 Mt.

On the other hand, the scenario “No cover crops” results in the largest decrease from the baseline with 41,79 Mt, followed by “No residues” with 53,65 Mt.

SLOVAKIA

A summary report of the ModelToolBox runs for Slovakia

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Simulations for Slovakia were carried out in two ways:

1. spatial approach using a 10 x 10 km grid
2. point approach at locations of the National Soil Inventory System

SIMULATION USING 10 x 10 km GRID

Spatial framework

- [EEA Reference grid](#) (10 km) – Slovakia is covered by 567 grids (fig. 1)

Figure 1: Coverage of the Slovak Republic territory by grid 10 x 10 km of EEA Reference grid system

Each grid was identified by three ID numbers (fig. 2):

1. **mtb ID** - identifier for simulation in ModelToolBox
2. **district ID** - district identifier (administrative unit). The district affiliation was used to determine the yields of individual crops
3. **production area ID** - production area identifier. The production area affiliation was used to determine the sowing and harvest date.

Figure 2: Attribute identification of 10 x 10 km grids

Crop rotation

The determination of crop rotation was carried out based on LPIS (2000 – 2017) and GSAA (2018 – 2020) spatial data (fig. 3). The [Land Parcel Identification System](#) (LPIS) is a reference database of the agriculture parcels used as a basis for area related payments to farmers in relation to the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). The [GeoSpatial Aid Application](#) (GSAA) is subsystem of IACS, defined by Art. 68 of Regulation 1306/2013. Provides delineation of agricultural parcels with cultivated crop or crop groups as submitted by the farmer in a given year.

Figure 3: Example of spatial extension of LPIS (green) and GSAA (blue) systems.

Each grid was assigned the crop with the largest spatial coverage.

Input data

As mentioned above, the territory of Slovakia is covered by 567 10 x 10 km grids. However, 21 of them do not cover the agricultural landscape and were therefore excluded from the simulation (fig. 4).

Figure 4: Spatial intersection of the agricultural landscape of Slovakia and the reference grid 10 x 10 km. Hatched grids are not covering agricultural land.

Data sources - CROP:

- ID: EEA Reference grid (10 km)
- NUM: 2000 - 2020
- SOWING_DATE: average date according to production areas
- HARVEST_DATE: average date according to production areas
- CROP: LPIS, GSAA
- CI_CC: no data
- Irrig: no data
- Yield: administrative district average (2000 – 2010)
- EOM_C: 10 km grids average (2009 – 2011)
- EOM_TYPE: only AnimalManure
- BIOCHAR_C: no data
- prop_residue_removal: estimated
- C_WOODY_ELEMENTS: no data

Data sources - SOIL:

- ID: EEA Reference grid (10 km)
- START_YEAR: 2000
- LON: grid centroid coordinate
- LAT: grid centroid coordinate
- CLAY: National Agricultural Soil Inventory - 1970
- OC_THA: National Soil Inventory System - 2002

Results

Figure 5: SOC overall development according to ModelToolBox simulation.

Figure 6: Spatial distribution of SOC overall development according to ModelToolBox simulation.

SIMULATION USING POINT DATA OF NATIONAL SOIL INVENTORY SYSTEM

Spatial framework

- National Soil Inventory System monitoring network includes **318** monitored sites on agricultural and alpine soils (all soil representatives, soil forming geological substrates, climatic regions, various types of land use, polluted and non-polluted areas are included). All monitored sites are located in JTSK and WGS 84 (fig. 7). The system is permanently running and developing since 1993 year. Sampling takes place in 5-year cycles (1993, 1997, 2002, 2007, 2013, 2018, 2023).

Figure 7: Soil monitoring sites network in Slovak Republic.

Each site was identified by three ID numbers (fig. 8):

4. **mtb ID** - identifier for simulation in ModelToolBox
5. **district ID** - district identifier (administrative unit). The district affiliation was used to determine the yields of individual crops
6. **production area ID** - production area identifier. The production area affiliation was used to determine the sowing and harvest date.

Figure 8: Attribute identification of sites

Crop rotation

The determination of crop rotation was carried out based on LPIS (2000 – 2017) and GSAA (2018 – 2020) spatial data (fig. 9). The [Land Parcel Identification System](#) (LPIS) is a reference database of the agriculture parcels used as a basis for area related payments to farmers in relation to the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). The [GeoSpatial Aid Application](#) (GSAA) is subsystem of IACS, defined by Art. 68 of Regulation 1306/2013. Provides delineation of agricultural parcels with cultivated crop or crop groups as submitted by the farmer each year.

Figure 9: Example of spatial extension intersection of LPIS (green) and GSAA (blue) systems and National Soil Inventory System site (red spot).

Each site was overlaid with the spatial extension of the LPIS and GSAA systems. Information about the cultivated crops was thus obtained. The only exceptions are the years of sampling (2002, 2007, 2013, 2018), when information about crops was obtained by field observations in situ.

Input data

As mentioned above, the territory of Slovakia is covered by 318 monitored sites on agricultural and alpine soils. However, 21 of them were excluded from the simulation (fig. 10) due to location (high mountainous locations) or land use (vineyards).

Figure 10: National Soil Inventory System monitoring network and simulation status of individual sites. Red spots were excluded from the simulation.

Data sources - CROP:

- ID: National Soil Inventory System monitoring network
- NUM: 2000 - 2019
- SOWING_DATE: average date according to production areas
- HARVEST_DATE: average date according to production areas
- CROP: National Inventory System, LPIS, GSAA
- CI_CC: no data
- Irrig: no data
- Yield: administrative district average (2000 – 2010)
- EOM_C: 10 km grids average (2009 – 2011)
- EOM_TYPE: only AnimalManure
- BIOCHAR_C: no data
- prop_residue_removal: estimated
- C_WOODY_ELEMENTS: no data

Data sources - SOIL:

- ID: National Soil Inventory System monitoring network
- START_YEAR: 2000
- LON: site coordinate
- LAT: site coordinate

- CLAY: National Soil Inventory System - 1993
- OC_THA: National Soil Inventory System - 2002

Results

Figure 11: SOC overall development according to ModelToolBox simulation compared with measured data from National Soil Inventory System.

Figure 12: Spatial distribution of SOC overall development according to ModelToolBox simulation (green spot – increase of SOC, red spot – decrease of SOC).

SLOVENIA

National simulations for CarboSeq

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Simulations for Slovenia were not run on the 10x10 km grid but for 12 strata (statistical regions). These regions differ mostly by the yield of crops, as well as by pedoclimatic conditions.

Figure 1: Statistical regions of Slovenia = simulation points

Table 1: Code of strata/regions used for simulations including coordinates and soil properties.

ID	code	LAT	LON	clay (%)	silt (%)	SOC (t C in upper 30 cm)	pH
1	ID1	46.6641756	16.18087811	23.25	50.76	75.78	5.82
2	ID2	46.47116992	15.75266266	23.78	50.77	73.89	5.86
3	ID3	46.53145617	15.08810293	18.40	41.35	59.80	5.00
4	ID4	46.2702884	15.19594491	28.01	54.02	87.08	5.93
5	ID5	46.0990647	14.96896809	16.83	51.08	68.85	5.74
6	ID6	45.96625552	15.43847172	33.34	51.78	86.67	6.51
7	ID7	45.70759022	15.02035983	25.12	60.63	80.22	5.97
8	ID8	46.0253405	14.56631927	26.20	52.95	113.24	6.43
9	ID9	46.30371491	14.13946118	20.89	48.24	95.68	6.33
10	ID10	45.68782998	14.30628772	29.29	47.23	104.83	6.21
11	ID11	46.08925365	13.77786068	26.32	51.71	74.37	7.03
12	ID12	45.62237026	13.8827095	30.19	47.28	66.27	7.39

Simulations were run for 4 crops separately. The crop cycle used is one of the few common national crop cycle practices.

Table 2: Crop types used for modelling at Slovenian level

cropCategory (winter/summer crop)	name	name csopralibs (MTB)
Wcrop	barley	WinterBarley
Wcrop	Clover-grass mixture	LegumeMixture
Scrop	Corn	SilageCorn
Wcrop	triticale	WinterTriticale

Yields of each crop for each statistical region were calculated from data obtained at Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia.

Description of soil.csv

As initial soil conditions, we used data gathered in 2 projects. 1 project was soil carbon national survey (started 2016), and the other is a national agricultural soil monitoring program (started 2022).

Only Croplands were considered, as we created the soil.csv file.

Parameters for each sampling (i.e., location) were recalculated as an average for the depth of 0 – 30 cm, except for Corg, where the total carbon stock from 0 – 30 cm (t/ha) was calculated. All parameters were calculated as averages per statistical region, and the X and Y coordinates, and N and E coordinates of the region's centroid were added.

Normalization of regional soil data – Average values of selected parameters from field sampling data at a depth of 0 – 30 cm, n=191 locations) at the level of the statistical region.
Coordinates - Average values of selected parameters (from field sampling data at a depth of 0 – 30 cm) at the level of the statistical region, presented in the WGS84 coordinate system with assigned N and E coordinates.

Description of scenarios

For all the scenarios we left the farmyard manure inputs unchanged, and were the same as in Baseline scenario.

Baseline (on JupyterLab: Baseline)

Year 1: Winter Barley

(applied composted bovine solid manure of 35 t/ha = 1.54 tC-org./ha).

Straw removed from the field.

Sowing date à 01-10

Harvest date à 25-06

Year 2: Legume Mixture

Sowing date à 01-08

Harvest date à 25-09

Year 3: Silage Corn

(applied composted bovine solid manure of 35 t/ha = 1.54 tC-org./ha).

Crop residues removed from the field.
Sowing date à 25-04
Harvest date à 15-09

Year 4: Winter Triticale.
Crop residues left on the field.
Sowing date à 10-10
Harvest date à 15-07

Due to the crop cycle used, we didn't use cover crops in the baseline scenario, therefore à baseline = No_Covercrops.

No_Residues (on JupyterLab: No_Residues)

All residues were removed for 4 types of crops.

Pot_Residues (on JupyterLab: Pot_Residues)

In Slovenia, sometimes the straw is left on the field, but other times it's removed. Therefore in the baseline scenario only Winter Triticale straw was left on the field.

In the Pot_Residues scenario we put 0 also for Winter Wheat crop. Silage corn can not have residues left, because the whole crop is harvested.

Pot_Covercrop (on JupyterLab: Pot_Cover)

After the Legume Mixture we added additional cover crop.

Pot_Ley (on JupyterLab: Pot_Ley)

Silage maize was replaced by perennial ley ("LegumeMixture").

Pot_Biochar (on JupyterLab: ch_biochar_pot)

All crops receive same amount of biochar: 1.87 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Regions/strata with pH =>7 were excluded (ID= 11 and 11).

Description of results

Results are delivered for each scenario and are delivered for each stratum/region ("Cropland_SOC_allStrata....csv) and for the national scale (SOC_national... csv). The strata codes are described in "coordinates_strata...". The file "summary_allScenarios csv" contains the SOC changes for 20 years in t C ha⁻¹ (dSOC).

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Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia. 10.12.2024 ([SURS](#))

SWEDEN

A summary report of the ModelToolBox runs for Sweden

Benjamin Bukombe, Martin Bolinder, Thomas Kätterer

Data input

In this document, we will summarize the ModelToolBox input data and source for Sweden. Briefly, the input data we used for ModelToolBox are for eight Swedish agricultural production (PO8) regions (Fig. 1). Therefore, the results are also presented at the regional level and later aggregated at the national level. The soil data in the “soil.csv” were derived from the national soil-monitoring program and existing reports developed by the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency in collaboration with the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Bolinder et al., 2022). All data in the “crop.csv” file including the crop yields, manure, residue management, and cover crop data are based on the annual agricultural census and a series of reports published by Statistics Sweden (“Use of fertilizers and animal manure in agriculture”), Gödselmedelsunderökningen (GMU). The GMU reports the total amount of manure spread on arable land for different livestock categories and types of manure storage forms. Note that for the ModelToolBox we use the sum of the liquid and solid manure because the model does not receive two different types of manure.

Crop rotations for ModelToolBox

We used crop data from reports and national surveys to create crop rotations for model runs. As follows:

1. **Identify crops:** For each year and region, we included a crop if it covered more than 3% of the total arable land.
2. **Calculate proportions:** We calculated the annual proportion cover of each crop and the average proportion over 20 years in each region.
3. **Select crops for rotation:** For each year, we picked the crop with the highest percentage but considering that its overall frequency over 20 years does not exceed the proportion calculated in setp2.

Figure 1: Swedish production regions used for the ModelToolBox runs. Source: Bolinder et al, 2022.

This approach ensured that major crops made up about 80% of the rotation sequence and gave more weight to crops that were used frequently and that covered large areas.

Scenarios

We ran simulations for five scenarios as described in the "**How_to_MTB.docx**" document. We would like to highlight one specific scenario the "Pot_Covercrop". This scenario was calculated based on the methods suggested by (Barrios Latorre et al., 2024).

Reformulated equation to directly estimate the total area available for IC:

$$IC_{area} = 1.264 * SC_{area} + 0.204 * WC_{area} - 0.119 * LR_{area} \text{ (Eq. D.2)}$$

IC_{area} : total area available for cultivation of IC

LR_{area} : total area of arable land under rotation.

SC_{area} : total area occupied by spring crops

WC_{area} : total area occupied by winter cereals.

Files uploaded

All files were prepared based on the extended email from Julien “[CarboSeq] **LAST update of the MTB + IMPORTANT infos**”. File naming followed the guidelines described in the “**How_to_MTB.docx**”. Note that the attribute tables of “.shp” files have results of all scenarios for all years.

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SWITZERLAND

National simulations for CarboSeq

Sonja G. Keel and Chloé Wüst-Galley

sonja.keel@agroscope.admin.ch, 02.12.2024

Simulations for Switzerland were not run on the 10x10 km grid but for 18 strata (pedoclimatic regions with similar, agricultural management). These regions differ strongly regarding their size (see map) and are described in Wüst et al. 2020.

Figure 17: The four AZs used in this project; AZ boundaries © FOAG.

Figure 19: The 24 strata obtained from a union of the AZs and NFI regions.

Fig. 1: The four agricultural zones (top panel) and six climate zones (central panel) were combined to form 24 strata/regions (lowest panel), which are our simulation units. For CarboSeq four regions in the summer pasture zone were left away.

As initial soil conditions, weighted average SOC stocks were calculated by Chloé Wüst-Galley for these regions based on a digital soil map for the years 1998-2002 (Stumpf et al. 2023; Stumpf et al. unpublished). The lat / lon values were also calculated by her using the 'feature to point' tool in ArcGIS Pro, with 'inside' option activated.

Table 1: Code of strata/regions used for simulations including coordinates and soil properties.

ID	code	CoordX	CoordY	X_dd	Y_dd	FREQUENCY	silt (%)	pH	clay (%)	SOC_2000 (t C in upper 30 cm)
1	A1_F1	2594600	1243400	7.36717082	47.3414341	44616	41.4095697	6.49537842	28.0265999	57.63872464
2	A1_F2	2613600	1215900	7.61775801	47.0939658	237496	33.7742876	6.35855529	22.7381537	57.90467452
3	A1_F3	2695000	1228800	8.69250337	47.2033145	10907	37.9387218	6.34559399	27.8999757	72.79307723
4	A1_F4_C	2758400	1206500	9.52117229	46.9906451	3263	44.1134182	7.02166338	19.4793803	56.00451757
5	A1_F4_W	2561200	1130100	6.93486901	46.3211727	4767	40.2508811	6.76132382	25.2027167	61.4556287
6	A1_F5	2714900	1112700	8.92605017	46.1559817	1607	35.990497	6.23887817	24.4802699	64.98910529
7	A2_F1	2629800	1256100	7.83379082	47.455011	14745	38.0263518	6.56700052	33.5946146	62.4810028
8	A2_F2	2601200	1194100	7.45438114	46.8980101	29908	33.5601296	6.15685629	23.6349695	61.12533161
9	A2_F3	2620600	1204200	7.70942533	46.9885446	6557	33.5586605	6.17873238	24.499556	64.77825365
10	A2_F4_C	2748200	1185800	9.38039123	46.8068577	1564	41.6252176	7.09655858	17.2661383	47.92304522
11	A2_F4_W	2634000	1170500	7.88306381	46.6848568	177	39.864949	6.65150665	22.8158397	60.86528869
12	A2_F5	2719800	1125900	8.99285054	46.2738471	299	36.6627224	6.35546189	23.2999111	56.22932594
13	A3_F1	2576100	1227000	7.12324984	47.1935115	11632	37.3835376	6.31291478	31.0568157	62.04094865
14	A3_F2	2592000	1187800	7.33375983	46.8412917	2958	34.0184095	6.08558106	24.7003643	61.64081563
15	A3_F3	2615000	1191000	7.63537858	46.8669958	7686	33.111265	5.94236164	23.7655805	64.68811921
16	A3_F4_C	2752900	1178100	9.4393731	46.7365526	1676	36.2039436	6.60888931	19.0863819	51.76828966
17	A3_F4_W	2651000	1176500	8.10593484	46.737746	237	40.2339007	6.51299834	21.3201323	59.0727156
18	A3_F5	2718100	1131700	8.97227228	46.3263126	274	37.4159229	6.35430378	20.8256239	47.0820327

Comparison of weather data

Because the simulations units (strata) are large, we compared the weather data that is used for the Swiss greenhouse gas inventory with the forcing used here. For ID 2 which is the largest simulation unit and includes about 60% of Switzerland's cropland the weather data agrees well.

Figure 2: Comparison of weather data used here and in the Swiss greenhouse gas inventory.

Our experience is that weather is less critical for soil carbon sequestration than for estimating SOC stocks (Fig. 3). The reason is that both the baseline and the sequestration scenario are affected by the same weather.

Fig. 3: Figures from Keel et al. 2023 showing the large effect of different climate change scenarios on SOC stocks and the smaller effect on sequestration rates (calculated as difference between cover crop scenario and baseline).

Simulations were run for 19 crops separately and area-weighted mean SOC stocks were calculated as described in Wüst et al. 2020.

Table 2: Dominant crop types of Switzerland

croptype	cropCategory (winter/summer crop)	name	name csopralibs (MTB)
BA	Wcrop	barley	Winter barley
BB	Scrop	broad beans ("Ackerbohnen")	Vicia faba
FA	Scrop	fallow	Fallow land
FB	Scrop	fodder beet	Fodder beets
GM	Scrop	clover-grass (ley)	Legume(whole)
MA	Scrop	maize (grain)	Grain corn
OA	Scrop	oat	Avena sativa
PE	Scrop	peas ("Eiweisserbsen")	Pisum sativum
PO	Scrop	potatoes	Solanum tuberosum
RA	Wcrop	rape (cooking oil)	Brassica napus subsp. napus
RY	Wcrop	rye	Winter rye
SB	Scrop	sugar beet	Sugar beets
SC	Scrop	silage and green corn	Silage corn
SF	Scrop	sun flowers (cooking oil)	Helianthus annuus
SO	Scrop	soybean	GlycineMax
SP	Wcrop	spelt (Dinkel)	TriticumSpelta
TR	Wcrop	triticale	Winter triticale
VE	Scrop	vegetables	DaucusCarotaSubsp.Sativus
WH	Wcrop	wheat	Winter wheat

Description of input data

Generally, most data used for the simulations are the same as used for national greenhouse gas reporting and is available for the national scale (FOEN 2024). Briefly, annual crop yields (dt ha⁻¹) were obtained from the Swiss Farmers Union, annual carbon inputs from organic manures to different types of crops were calculated based on: (1) organic manure production, (2) animal herd size, (3) the share of manure management systems, and (4) the tendency of farmers to apply different types of manure onto four different crop categories, (5) the different fertilisation needs of individual crops and (6) straw production, using annual values published by the Swiss Farmers Union.

Description of scenarios

Baseline (on JupyterLab: doesn't exist)

For winter crops and grasslands in the rotation (FA,GM) baseline simulations are identical with simulations for cov_no or cov_pot.

For summer crops a weighted mean SOC was calculated based on the annual output for each summer crop.

Covercrop_no had a weight of 0.67 and covercrop_pot a weight of 0.33. The reason for this is that setting cover_crops to yes (or 1) for the simulations led to very high C inputs of 2 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. In Switzerland a C input of only about 0.5-0.7 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ is used for the greenhouse gas inventory and around 2 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ is rather the potential (Keel et al. 2023). The weighting results in a C input that is 0.66 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹.

No_Residues (on JupyterLab: ch_res_no)

All residues were removed for six types of cereals (BA, OA, RY, SP, TR, WH). We left farmyard manure inputs unchanged. However, they actually contain the cereal straw.

Pot_Residues (on JupyterLab: ch_res_pot)

In Switzerland the common practice is that all residues remain on/are returned to the field. In the first case this is mainly important for rapeseed, grain corn, sunflowers but also true for potato, sugar beets etc. In the case of cereals, the common practice is that all straw is removed, used for animal bedding and returned to the field as farmyard manure (i.e. straw plus animal excreta).

Because the common practice is already the potential, the simulations for the baseline and pot_residues are identical.

No_Covercrop (on JupyterLab: ch_cov_no)

Summer crops (BB, FA, FB etc., see Table 2) have no cover crops. (all other crops anyway don't have cover crops).

Pot_Covercrop (on JupyterLab: ch_base)

All summer crops have cover crops.

Note: On JupyterHub this was the baseline scenario. It was renamed on 29.11.2024 because C inputs for cover crops are very high (2tC ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) and hence rather reflect the cov_pot scenario.

Pot_Ley (on JupyterLab: ch_ley_pot)

Silage maize was replaced by perennial ley ("Legume(whole)"). Yields and organic fertilization rates typical for leys were used (about 1.5 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹). Note: silage maize

receives about 2.5 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ of organic fertilization. This means that not only the C inputs for the plants change, but also rates of organic fertilization are reduced in this scenario.

Pot_Biochar (on JupyterLab: ch_biochar_pot)

All crops receive same amount of biochar: 1.87 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Regions/strata with pH >7 were excluded (ID= 4 and 10).

Description of results

The simulated carbon stocks for each crop type and region were then upscaled using the proportion of different crop types within each region, as well as the surface of each region, to calculate weighted means (Wüst-Galley et al. 2020).

Results are delivered for each scenario and are delivered for each stratum/region ("Cropland_SOC_allStrata....csv") and for the national scale (SOC_national... csv). The strata codes are described in "coordinates_strata...". The file "summary_allScenarios csv" contains the SOC changes for 20 years in t C ha⁻¹ (dSOC), the normalized SOC changes/response ratios (dSOC_norm) and emission factors (EF). How these were calculated is described in the file "Example_dSOC_RR_EF_calculations". I hope this is correct.

References

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THE NETHERLANDS

Model Toolbox run for the Netherlands

Estimation of carbon sequestration potentials

Internal document of the EJP SOIL project CarboSeq

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Input data

Simulations for the Netherlands were run for 535 datapoints (284 on cropland and 251 on grassland) from the Dutch national monitoring campaign (Knotters et al., 2022)¹. The organic carbon stock and clay content of soils was taken from this national monitoring data. Other required model inputs such as crop type, sowing date, harvest date, yield, residue removal fraction, organic fertilizer C input and cover crop data were derived from an ESA funded project (EO4CSM, [An Earth Observation framework for soil carbon sequestration monitoring \(EO4CSM\) - WUR](#)) and national data as described in Lesschen et al. (2021)². This project has data from 2018-2022 (five years) and thus the data was looped four times in order to create a dataset of 20 years. The EOM_TYPE was always bovine slurry for straw crops and pig slurry for all other crops. As we do not have data for irrigation, biochar and C_WOODY_ELEMENTS, the values in these columns were all set to 0.

Grassland and perennial crops

For all grasslands, the sowing date was set to January 1st and the harvest date to December 31st. Fruit trees (apples and pears) were also simulated as grasslands, as there was no suitable C_WOODY_ELEMENTS input data, and in the Netherlands, orchards normally have grass between the trees.

Output

The results were summarized and reported per agricultural region. Using the agricultural regions in the Netherlands as shown in Figure 1.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2022.115751>

² <https://doi.org/10.18174/557330>

Figure 1: The fourteen different agricultural regions of the Netherlands

Baseline

In order for the simulation to last exactly 20 years, the sowing date and harvest date of each crop had to occur in the same year. In the original data, some crops were sown in autumn and harvested the following year. Doing so in the input data would result in the modeltoolbox adding additional years to the simulation). In addition, cover crops were always zero in the last year (2019) and

As the SOC sequestration scenarios only have an effect on croplands, the output for grasslands is identical for the different scenarios.

No residues

In this scenario, a 1 was inserted into the column “prop_residue_removal” if the CROP is a cereal, indicating that all residues from cereals (straws) were removed. The differences in the input scenario can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Differences in column “prop_residue_removal” in the baseline and no residues scenarios

Value in “prop_residue_removal”	Number of rows (individual crop years (535 datapoints *20 years))			
	Baseline		No residues scenario	
0	9732		8468	
0.25	96	Graincorn		
0.43	188	SummerBarley		
0.5	56	AvenaSativa, BrassicaNapussubsp.Napus, SummerRye,	8	Brassica Napus Subsp. Napus

		SummerTriticale, TriticumSpelta	
0.62	628	SummerWheat, WinterWheat	
1			2224
Total	10700		10700

Pot_Residues

Here it is assumed that all residues of cereal crops (straw) remain in the field. For this, a 0 was inserted into the column "prop_residue_removal" if the corresponding CROP is a straw. The differences in the input scenario can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Differences in column "prop_residue_removal" in the baseline and potential residues scenarios

Value in "prop_residue_removal"		Number of rows (individual crop years (535 datapoints *20 years))	
		Baseline	Potential residues scenario
0		9732	10692
0.25	GrainCorn	96	
0.43	SummerBarley	188	
0.5	AvenaSativa, BrassicaNapusSubsp.Napus, SummerRye, SummerTriticale, TriticumSpelta	56	8
0.62	SummerWheat, WinterWheat	628	
Total		10700	10700

No Cover crop

All cover crops were omitted in this scenario (all values in the column "CI_CC" are equal to 0). The resulting change in the input file is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Differences in column "CI_CC" in the baseline and no covercrop scenarios

Value in "CI_CC"	Number of rows (individual crop years (535 datapoints *20 years))	
	Baseline	No covercrop scenario
0	8496	10700
1	2204	
Total	10700	10700

Potential_Covercrop

Where possible, a cover crop was inserted into the crop rotation. It was assumed that this was possible whenever main crop A is harvested before mid-October and main crop A+1 was sown after

the first of March in the following year (the same assumption as the one by Germany as described in the 'How_to_MTB' document). The resulting change in the input file is shown in Table 4.

To prevent that the simulation would run for another year (21 years instead of 20), the harvest date in the last simulation year (2019) for perennial crops was changed from 31 December to 30 November for this scenario.

Table 4: Differences in column "CI_CC" in the baseline and potential covercrop scenarios

Value in "CI_CC"	Number of rows (individual crop years (535 datapoints *20 years))	
	Baseline	Potential covercrop scenario
0	8496	7787
1	2204	2901
Total	10700	10700

Potential_Ley

In this scenario, all "SilageCorn" was replaced by "LegumeMixture" (Ley type 3) and the corresponding crop data (yield, manure, etc.) was adapted accordingly. The sowing date was assumed to be January 1st and the harvest date was assumed to be December 31st. Similarly to the Potential Covercrop scenario, the harvest date in the last simulation year (2019) was 30 November instead of 31 December, to ensure a simulation period of only 20 years.

Description of results

Table 5 shows the initial C stock, the change in C stock over the 20-year simulation period for the baseline scenario and the change in final C stock of the different scenarios compared to the baseline scenario for arable lands of the 14 different arable regions in the Netherlands. The table shows that the scenarios 'potential cover crop' and 'potential residues' have a positive result compared to the baseline scenario. The scenarios 'no cover crop', and 'no residues' have a negative result compared to the baseline scenario. The 'potential ley' scenario also results in a lower C sequestration scenario when compared to the baseline, in contrast expected SOC accrual effect that leys have. This is however likely due to the fact that the IPCC method was used to calculate C inputs, which is highly dependent on yield (and the yield of silage maize exceeds that of ley).

Table 5 : Initial C stock, change in C stock over 20-year simulation period for the baseline scenario, and the change in final C stock of the different scenarios compared to the baseline scenario for arable lands in the 14 different agricultural regions in the Netherlands.

FID	Initial C stock (tC/ha)	Change in C stock for baseline scenario (tC/ha)	Change in final C stock of different scenarios compared to the baseline scenario (tC/ha)				
			No cover crop	Potential cover crop	No residues	Potential residues	Potential ley
0	66.46	0.07	-5.30	4.50	-1.59	2.02	0.38
1	102.63	-14.51	-6.12	5.60	-2.27	3.09	-0.64
2	109.40	-10.50	-9.62	2.14	-0.83	0.14	-6.52
3	87.56	-3.94	-10.62	1.33	-1.43	0.69	-7.50

4	93.18	-4.35	-8.10	0.76	-1.34	0.56	-4.98
5	64.92	-2.16	-7.92	5.23	-1.19	1.58	0.42
6	83.89	-8.10	-4.55	6.22	-1.19	1.52	0.58
7	92.29	-8.72	0.00	2.59	-0.91	0.00	-0.78
8	158.10	-22.55	-2.38	3.18	-1.14	0.00	-0.81
9	85.21	-7.86	-3.78	1.27	-2.19	0.74	-3.20
10	60.04	1.93	-7.74	3.50	-2.52	3.57	-0.02
11	77.59	-7.70	-9.54	3.95	-1.04	0.73	-3.03
12	74.58	-3.29	-9.71	2.38	-1.75	1.01	-3.67
13	59.42	3.81	-10.40	3.27	-2.79	3.62	-2.16

The initial and final C stocks of the baseline scenario for grasslands are shown in Table 6. As the other scenarios only impact arable lands, the final C stocks of those scenarios for grasslands are identical to those of the baseline scenario, and therefore not shown.

Table 6 Initial C stock and change in C stock over 20-year simulation period for the baseline scenario of grasslands in the 14 different agricultural regions in the Netherlands.

FID	Initial C stock (tC/ha)	Change in C stock for baseline scenario (tC/ha)
0	103.87	-2.04
1	113.68	-7.01
2	112.52	-6.72
3	94.96	-4.32
4	111.69	-8.19
5	76.77	3.61
6	117.93	-6.51
7	153.46	-12.78
8	144.33	-11.39
9	104.10	-2.78
10	100.25	-5.48
11	87.70	-5.78
12	85.70	-6.45
13	74.91	0.73

An overview of the change in C stock (tC/ha) compared to the first year (2000), for the baseline scenario is shown in Figure 2. Additionally, the trend for arable lands for each scenario is shown in Figure 3.

Further results are provided in the “results” folder. The initial and final SOC stock is given for both arable lands (initial_final_stocks_arable.csv) and grasslands (initial_final_stocks_grass.csv) for each of the agricultural regions (with the initial SOC stock being identical for each scenario). The shapefiles of the agricultural regions are also provided in the folder “results”.

Figure 2 : SOC change since 2000 (tC/ha) for arable land and grassland in the baseline scenario, the black line shows the average trend.

Figure 3: SOC change since 2000 (tC/ha) for arable land in the different scenarios. The black line shows the average trend.

SOC-sequestration potential in Italy

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Based on the last instructions received during the meeting held in Koln, in September 2024, the national runs for Italy were restricted to 3 measures, each with 2 or 3 versions (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Measures for which the national runs were made for Italy.

1. Common information used for the three measures

Soil properties: Soil properties were derived from INSPIRE data layers (raster GRID maps (cell 10 km x 10 km) <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/projects/inspire-and-soil-data>). The INSPIRE database, in vectorial format, contains, for the upper 30 cm soil layer, the following pedological information:

- Clay content (%),
- Silt content (%),
- SOC stock value (Mg ha^{-1}).

Land-use map: for each cell of the INSPIRE grid, the main land-use according to Corine Land Cover (2020) map and the respective coverage percentage (0-100) is provided. The cells classified as “Cropland, rainfed” or as “Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding” were selected to run the simulation of the SOC dynamics over time (nearly 1800 cells). The cells were grouped into the 20 Italian administrative regions to properly interoperate with more specific data about crops cultivation retrieved from ISTAT (see below). On each of these cells, the average values of clay and SOC stock content of the upper 30 cm soil layer were calculated.

Since the sum of the agricultural areas in the INSPIRE grid cells (10 x 10 km) for Italy largely exceeded the actual national arable lands area, a downscaling factor, variable among regions, was applied to restore the surfaces to their actual size. In this way, the correspondence between the cell areas subjected to simulations and the arable lands of each region was guaranteed. This procedure was necessary i) to provide realistic estimations on SOC sequestration potential at national level and ii) because the methodology employed to define the “current” and the “potential” scenarios is based on the organic agriculture arable land areas present in each region on two dates: 2013 and 2022 (Tab. 1) (see the chapters of each scenario for more details).

Crops cultivation surface data: 2010 – 2020 average surface (ha) as described in the portal of the National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT, [Crops \(istat.it\)](https://www.istat.it)), for each Italian Region.

Crops yield data: 2010 – 2020 average yield as described in the portal of the National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT, [Crops \(istat.it\)](https://www.istat.it)), for each Italian Region.

Implementation of organic agriculture: level of implementation in each Italian Region in 2013 and 2022 as described in two reports made by ISMEA and CIHEAM (Cecchini, V., et al., 2024; De Matthaes, T., et al., 2014).

Tab. 1: Arable land surface of INSPIRE cells (ha) and ISTAT (ha), % of organic agriculture area in 2013 and 2022 and downscaling factor for each Italian Region. (Source: elaboration of the authors of the INSPIRE grid, ISTAT, Cecchini, V., et al., 2024; De Matthaeis, T., et al., 2014)

Region	INSPIRE grid arable land (ha)	ISTAT arable land (ha)	Downscaling factor	Organic agriculture area (% , 2013)	Organic agriculture area (% , 2022)
Abruzzo	461800	179000	0.39	6.06	9.02
Apulia	1684390	655000	0.39	11.51	18.25
Basilicata	685010	304000	0.44	9.11	25.35
Calabria	680650	164000	0.24	17.73	27.96
Campania	625150	269000	0.43	1.81	12.58
Emilia-Romagna	1442120	815000	0.57	6.51	15.11
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	332930	160000	0.48	0.87	3.97
Lazio	897830	299000	0.33	14.65	23.08
Liguria	11600	8000	0.69	2.30	5.85
Lombardy	1028260	684000	0.67	2.09	5.96
Marche	651770	363000	0.56	9.72	18.91
Molise	296370	133000	0.45	2.58	5.56
Piedmont	989840	509000	0.51	2.30	4.08
Sardinia	1277950	385000	0.30	7.85	8.32
Sicily	2156710	679000	0.31	14.42	19.19
Tuscany	883560	458000	0.52	10.00	25.63
Trentino-Alto Adige	49970	7000	0.14	9.79	10.13
Umbria	397790	202000	0.51	7.07	10.58
Veneto	1103360	554000	0.50	1.14	4.24
Total	15657060	6827000	0.44	7.42	13.98

After having carried out the simulations on carbon dynamics for the different measures, the next step was to define the “current” and the “potential” scenarios, trying to illustrate level of measures applications that can be defined plausible currently and potentially.

SOC dynamics were simulated with the RothC model version adapted to the Mediterranean areas (RothC10_N, Farina et al., 2013).

For each measure, the simulation of SOC dynamics providing the lowest SOC stock, after 20 years of agricultural management, (MIN SOC STOCK, eq. [1]) was the one describing conventional agriculture and the highest SOC stock (MAX SOC STOCK, eq. [1]) was the one describing organic agriculture.

Having said that, for both scenarios, current and potential, in the same INSPIRE cell there is a combination of conventional and organic arable land, whose relative abundance depends on the % area of organic agriculture surveyed in 2013 and 2022, respectively.

Hence, for each INSPIRE cell and measure the SOC stock was calculated by applying the following equation:

$$SOC\ STOCK_{CELL} = \frac{(MIN\ SOC\ STOCK * (Conventional\ Area) + MAX\ SOC\ STOCK * (Organic\ Area))}{Arable\ Land\ Area} \quad [1]$$

Where the Organic Area corresponds to the one surveyed in Italy for 2013, for the current scenario, and the one surveyed in 2022, for the potential scenario.

Climate data: mean monthly rainfall, temperature and evapotranspiration were derived from a 25 km x 25 km grid-based climate dataset available from the Joint Research Centre (<http://mars.jrc.ec.europa.eu/mars/About-us/AGRI4CAST>) and validated using locally observed data.

In Tab. 2 we summarize the main soil and climate properties of the twenty Italian regions together with their arable land surface and average altitude.

Tab. 2: Arable land surface, average altitude, climate and soil properties of the twenty Italian regions (Source: elaboration of the authors of the INSPIRE grid and AGRI4CAST)

Region	Arable land (ha)	Average altitude (m a.s.l)	T (°C)	P (mm)	Eto (mm)	Clay (%)	SOC Stock (Mg ha ⁻¹)
Abruzzo	179000	316 (244)	14.3 (1.4)	668 (63)	1020 (26)	33.7 (3.9)	57.63 (10.81)
Basilicata	304000	418 (251)	15.5 (1.2)	562 (33)	1145 (65)	33.6 (1.7)	55.12 (14.87)
Calabria	164000	223 (154)	17.2 (1.6)	649 (58)	1220 (77)	31.9 (2.4)	60.19 (10.82)
Campania	269000	382 (247)	16 (1.2)	623 (58)	1067 (66)	33.2 (2.6)	61.68 (12.67)
Emilia-Romagna	815000	86 (121)	14.3 (0.4)	709 (60)	953 (46)	33.1 (2.7)	50.29 (11)
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	160000	70 (72)	14.1 (0.4)	1054 (75)	931 (16)	24.4 (1.2)	55.43 (11.6)
Lazio	299000	175 (143)	16 (0.9)	703 (64)	1088 (47)	31.4 (2.1)	57.01 (11.7)
Liguria	8000	265 (27)	16.4 (0)	709 (0)	1112 (0)	34 (0.4)	72.05 (7.57)
Lombardy	684000	80 (60)	14.5 (0.2)	803 (55)	926 (19)	25.8 (4)	46.51 (6.78)
Marche	363000	229 (146)	14.7 (0.4)	704 (60)	1010 (29)	35.2 (1.9)	56.14 (14.55)
Molise	133000	434 (224)	15.5 (1.1)	556 (76)	1016 (88)	35.6 (2.8)	61.04 (13.11)
Piedmont	509000	248 (111)	13.5 (1.9)	795 (38)	958 (68)	27 (4)	51.51 (8.02)
Apulia	655000	180 (158)	16.3 (1)	529 (49)	1170 (51)	32.7 (2.8)	47.55 (7.84)
Sardinia	385000	259 (199)	16.9 (1.5)	465 (63)	1233 (76)	29.7 (3.3)	58.04 (10.82)
Sicily	679000	357 (231)	17.3 (1)	482 (53)	1260 (61)	33.8 (2.7)	57.06 (10.86)
Tuscany	458000	184 (130)	15.1 (0.8)	690 (81)	1058 (82)	33.2 (2.9)	55.06 (8.32)
Trentino-Alto Adige	7000	688 (81)	11.4 (0.4)	878 (7)	856 (13)	20.7 (1.5)	106.4 (10.92)
Umbria	202000	357 (135)	14.3 (1)	749 (46)	1063 (58)	32.5 (1.7)	62.99 (14.94)
Veneto	554000	37 (66)	14.5 (0.3)	835 (111)	914 (25)	27.4 (3.2)	51.79 (11.05)
Total Italian arable land	6827000	227 (205)	15.6 (1.6)	641 (150)	1093 (136)	31.5 (4.1)	54.65 (12.02)

2. Measures

2.1 Cover crops

To simulate the application of cover crops throughout the Italian territory, it was necessary to find a crop that was widespread all over the peninsula and that could include cover crops in the yearly agricultural management plan, to improve edaphic properties. The choice fell on a short-cycle summer crop, a vegetable, which, leaving the soil bare in the autumn-winter period, required the introduction of another crop capable of restoring the fertility of the soil, and or protect the soil by erosion process. Among vegetables, the industrial tomato is the most widespread and is often included in a rotation with an autumn-winter cereal and a cover crop of legumes. In Fig. 1 the crop rotation scheme is described, with and without cover crops.

		YEAR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
ROTATION WITH LEGUMINOUS COVER CROPS (ORGANIC AGRICULTURE)	1													
	2													
	3													
	4													
	5													
		YEAR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
ROTATION WITHOUT LEGUMINOUS COVER CROPS (CONVENTIONAL AGRICULTURE)	1													
	2													
	3													
	4													
	5													

LEGUMINOUS COVER CROP (VETCH/TRIFOLIUM, OTHER LEGUM.)
AUTUMN-WINTER CEREALS (OAT, DURUM WHEAT, WINTER WHEAT, RYE)
TOMATO
BARE SOIL

Fig. 1: Crop rotation scheme (industrial tomato and autumn-winter cereal), with and without leguminous cover crops

Scenarios:

- **Without:** Italian arable land managed with conventional agriculture method.
- **Current:** Italian arable land managed with organic agriculture method as for 2013 (last year of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) programming period 2007 - 2013). The surface of organic agriculture implementation has been chosen as it is a surface where realistically the measure of cover crops is applied.
- **Potential:** Italian arable land managed with organic agriculture method as for 2022 (last year of the CAP 2014 - 2022). The 2014 – 2022 programming period is more ambitious than the previous one in terms of target areas of organic agriculture implementation and therefore can be seen as a potential compared to the previous CAP.

For each region, the yield of tomato and autumn-winter cereals were retrieved by the ISTAT dataset (Tab. 3).

Tab. 3: Yield of tomato and autumn winter cereals (Source: elaboration by the authors of ISTAT data)

Region	Five-year rotation	Autumn- winter cereal (2y)	Yield (Mg ha ⁻¹) FM	Vegetables (3y)	Yield (Mg ha ⁻¹) FM
Abruzzo	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Durum wheat	3.8	Industrial tomato	48.1
Apulia	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Durum wheat	3	Industrial tomato	81.2
Basilicata	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Durum wheat	3	Industrial tomato	55.8
Calabria	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Durum wheat	2.8	Industrial tomato	40.3
Campania	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Durum wheat	3	Industrial tomato	60.0
Emilia-Romagna	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Winter wheat	6.2	Industrial tomato	69.3
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Winter wheat	4.8	Industrial tomato	31.3
Lazio	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Durum wheat	3.2	Industrial tomato	61.3
Liguria	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Winter wheat	2.5	Industrial tomato	34.8
Lombardy	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Winter wheat	5.6	Industrial tomato	67.6
Marche	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Durum wheat	4.2	Industrial tomato	45.4
Molise	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Durum wheat	3.1	Industrial tomato	62.6
Piedmont	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Winter wheat	5.3	Industrial tomato	59.0
Sardinia	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Durum wheat	2.4	Industrial tomato	58.4
Sicily	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Durum wheat	2.8	Industrial tomato	16.6
Trentino-Alto Adige	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Rye	3.9	Industrial tomato	30.2
Tuscany	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Durum wheat	3.3	Industrial tomato	58.6
Umbria	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Winter wheat	6.1	Industrial tomato	57.6
Veneto	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Winter wheat	6.5	Industrial tomato	66.8

Based on yields and the formula described in Farina *et al.*, (2017), the C_{input} provided by the crop were calculated. More specifically, the C_{input} is in the form of carbon derived by roots and roots exudates from tomato and cereals. In the case of organic management, it is supposed that cover crops annually add 0.33 Mg ha⁻¹ to the soil according to Poeplau and Don (2015). No residues incorporation is considered in this scenario.

2.2 Crops residues management

To apply this practice throughout the Italian territory, it was necessary to find a crop that was widespread all over the peninsula with a significative yield in order to appreciate significative differences between the C_{input} of the scenarios with and without the addition of crop residues to the soil. The choice fell on the rotation of autumn-winter cereals as described in the AGRIT land parcels database (Di Bene et al., 2016) and summarized in Table 4.

Scenarios:

- **Without:** Italian arable land managed with conventional agriculture method.
- **Current:** Italian arable land managed with organic agriculture method as for 2013 (last year of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) programming period 2007 - 2013). The surface of organic agriculture implementation has been chosen as it is a surface where realistically the measure of crop residue management is applied.
- **Potential:** Italian arable land managed with organic agriculture method as for 2022 (last year of the CAP 2014 - 2022). The 2014 – 2022 programming period is more ambitious than the previous one in terms of target areas of organic agriculture implementation and therefore can be seen as a potential scenario for crop residue management compared to the previous CAP.

Based on the ISTAT and AGRIT data described above, the most frequent crop rotation for each Region was defined, as well as the most frequent autumn-winter cereals and the associated crop yields (Tab. 4).

Tab. 4: Most frequent crop rotation and most frequent autumn-winter cereals for each Italian Region and associated yields (Source: elaboration of the authors based on ISTAT and AGRIT data).

Region	Five-year rotation	Autumn- winter cereal	Yield (Mg ha ⁻¹) FM	Other crop (number of years during the 5-year rotation)	Yield (Mg ha ⁻¹) FM
Abruzzo	Autumn-winter cereals + Alfalfa	Durum wheat	3.8	Alfalfa (1y)	17.9
Apulia	Autumn-winter cereals + Tomato	Durum wheat	3	Tomato (1y)	81
Basilicata	Autumn-winter cereals + Set-aside	Durum wheat	3	Set -aside (1y)	
Calabria	Autumn-winter cereals + Set-aside	Durum wheat	2.8	Set -aside (1y)	
Campania	Autumn-winter cereals + Fodder crops	Durum wheat	3	Alfalfa (1y)	46.7
Emilia-Romagna	Autumn-winter cereals + Sugar beet	Winter wheat	6.2	Sugar beet (1y)	40.13
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	Autumn-winter cereals + Soya bean	Winter wheat	4.8	Soya bean (5y)	6.2
Lazio	Autumn-winter cereals + Fodder crops	Durum wheat	3.2	Alfalfa (1y)	16.6
Liguria	Autumn-winter cereals + Alfalfa	Winter wheat	2.5	Alfalfa (1y)	10.8
Lombardy	Autumn-winter cereals + Silage maize	Winter wheat	5.6	Silage maize (2y)	11.3
Marche	Autumn-winter cereals + Sunflower	Durum wheat	4.2	Sunflower (1y)	2.1
Molise	Autumn-winter cereals + Sunflower	Durum wheat	3.1	Sunflower (1y)	1.6
Piedmont	Autumn-winter cereals + Maize	Winter wheat	5.3	Maize (2y)	9.6
Sardinia	Autumn-winter cereals + Set-aside	Durum wheat	2.4	Set -aside (1y)	
Sicily	Autumn-winter cereals + Fodder crops	Durum wheat	2.8	Alfalfa (1y)	7.1
Trentino-Alto Adige	Autumn-winter cereals + Silage maize	Rye	3.9	Silage maize (2y)	3.8
Tuscany	Autumn-winter cereals + Maize	Durum wheat	3.3	Maize (1y)	7.8
Umbria	Autumn-winter cereals + Sunflower	Winter wheat	6.1	Sunflower (1y)	2.2
Veneto	Autumn-winter cereals + Maize	Winter wheat	6.5	Maize (1y)	9.7

2.3 Legume fodder crops/ley instead of maize

The objective of this simulation is to test to what extent greater use of a fodder legume instead of silage maize can increase the carbon stock in the soil. In particular, two five-year rotations were compared:

- i) standard silage maize management: given that continuous cropping of corn is not allowed, the rotation includes 3 years of silage maize (never consecutive) and two years of legume fodder crops followed by an autumn-winter cereal.
- ii) more virtuous silage maize management: 2 years of silage maize (never consecutive) and 3 years of legume fodder crops with autumn-winter cereals.

Silage maize yield for each region was retrieved from the ISTAT database. The choice of fodder legumes crops was region-based and focused on annual crops with good yields and high cultivated area (Tab. 5).

Scenarios:

- **Current:** Italian arable land managed with organic agriculture method as for 2013 (last year of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) programming period 2007 - 2013). The surface of organic agriculture implementation has been chosen as it is a surface where realistically the cultivation of legume fodder crops, instead of continuous maize, is applied.
- **Potential:** Italian arable land managed with organic agriculture method as for 2022 (last year of the CAP 2014 - 2022). The 2014 – 2022 programming period is more ambitious than the previous one in terms of target areas of organic agriculture implementation and therefore can be seen as a potential scenario for legume fodder crops compared to the previous CAP.

Tab. 5: Yield of silage maize, winter wheat and leguminous fodder crops (Source: elaboration by the authors of ISTAT data)

Region	Yield (Mg ha ⁻¹) FM		Yield (Mg ha ⁻¹) FM	
	Silage maize	Winter wheat	Leguminous fodder crops	
Abruzzo	48.29	4.29	Soya bean	3.02
Apulia	37.23	2.50	Soya bean	2.42
Basilicata	25.88	2.63	Other legumes	15.90
Calabria	34.71	2.84	Soya bean	3.92
Campania	48.63	3.48	Soya bean	3.03
Emilia	52.33	6.22	Soya bean	3.55
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	37.44	4.81	Soya bean	4.15
Lazio	47.58	3.67	Soya bean	1.81
Liguria	23.41	2.54	Other legumes	13.33
Lombardy	55.41	5.64	Soya bean	3.64
Marche	38.95	4.75	Soya bean	2.89
Molise	40.35	2.40	Other legumes	5.85
Piedmont	42.65	5.31	Soya bean	2.89
Sardinia	34.44	2.42	Other legumes	13.95
Sicily	17.03	2.50	Sulla	7.10
Trentino-Alto Adige	62.96	3.82	Other legumes	40.97
Tuscany	44.44	3.45	Soya bean	2.42
Umbria	27.66	6.13	Soya bean	2.03
Veneto	47.46	6.48	Soya bean	3.51

3. Results

3.1 Cover crops

The simulation of SOC dynamics in the case of application of legumes cover crops within a five-year rotation of industrial tomato and autumn-winter cereals illustrates an overall reduction in soil carbon levels after 20 years (Tab. 6), very similar to the scenario where cover crops are not included.

This minimum impact on SOC STOCK might be explained by the fact that the simulation considers that the only sources of C_{input} for this measure are the roots and root exudates of the main crops (tomato and cereal) and, when present, 0.33 t ha^{-1} of C from cover crops (Poeplau and Don, 2015). This value, even if positive, seems to be too small to account for all the positive effect of cover crops in terms of soil carbon sequestration (Chahal et al., 2020) and protection from erosive phenomena in the autumn and winter period, thanks to soil coverage. Finally, the C_{input} deriving from the main crop residues are also excluded.

Based on this methodology, the addition of cover crops loses the expected effectiveness, and even in the more virtuous scenario (potential), only a small reduction in SOC losses is observed (Tab. 6).

Tab.6 Initial SOC STOCK average values (Mg ha^{-1}) and simulated values for different scenarios in the case of cover crops management, at regional and level, and yearly SOC change ($\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$).

Region	SOC STOCK (Mg ha^{-1})				Δ SOC/ 20 years ($\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)		
	Initial	No	Current	Potential	No	Current	Potential
Abruzzo	57.63	49.89	49.98	50.02	-0.39	-0.38	-0.38
Apulia	47.55	41.36	41.51	41.59	-0.31	-0.30	-0.30
Basilicata	55.17	47.28	47.40	47.61	-0.39	-0.39	-0.38
Calabria	60.20	50.01	50.23	50.36	-0.51	-0.50	-0.49
Campania	61.68	52.08	52.10	52.24	-0.48	-0.48	-0.47
Emilia-Romagna	50.29	47.44	47.58	47.76	-0.14	-0.14	-0.13
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	55.43	49.04	49.05	49.10	-0.32	-0.32	-0.32
Lazio	57.01	48.81	49.00	49.11	-0.41	-0.40	-0.39
Liguria	72.05	60.93	60.96	61.01	-0.56	-0.55	-0.55
Lombardy	46.51	43.84	43.88	43.94	-0.13	-0.13	-0.13
Marche	56.14	49.03	49.18	49.32	-0.36	-0.35	-0.34
Molise	61.04	51.21	51.27	51.34	-0.49	-0.49	-0.48
Piedmont	51.51	46.98	47.02	47.05	-0.23	-0.22	-0.22
Sardinia	58.04	47.93	48.02	48.02	-0.51	-0.50	-0.50
Sicily	57.06	46.51	46.64	46.68	-0.53	-0.52	-0.52
Trentino-Alto Adige	106.40	90.94	91.04	91.04	-0.77	-0.77	-0.77
Tuscany	55.06	49.31	49.41	49.56	-0.29	-0.28	-0.27
Umbria	62.99	58.54	58.63	58.68	-0.22	-0.22	-0.22
Veneto	51.79	49.21	49.21	49.22	-0.13	-0.13	-0.13
Italy	54.65	43.27	43.43	43.55	-0.57	-0.56	-0.56

3.2 Crops residues management

The simulation of SOC dynamics in the case of 20-year autumn-winter cereals cultivation, in rotation with the crops described in Tab. 4, illustrate, on average at national level, a reduction in SOC levels both if residues are removed from the soil or if they are left on the soil (between -0.18 and -0.20 Mg ha⁻¹ SOC loss per year, Tab. 7). However, in four regions we observed SOC sequestration: Emilia Romagna, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Piedmont and Veneto. This might be explained with the high yield of the crops involved in the rotation compared to the other Italian regions (Tab.4).

The introduction of residues (current and potential scenarios vs. residues removal) only slightly reduced SOC losses, because the efficacy of the measure is reduced by the low percentage area of organic agriculture compared to conventional agriculture within the INSPIRE cells (Tab. 1).

The largest SOC STOCK loss was observed in Trentino-Alto Adige where the starting SOC value was particularly high, probably suggesting the presence of a soil typical of a natural environment (forest or grassland rather than cropland). Therefore, it is presumable that such a soil cannot maintain its equilibrium with a twenty-years rotation with autumn-winter cereals. Rather, it is plausible that a pasture or a pasture meadow would have better preserved the initial properties of the soil.

High SOC STOCK reduction (on average 0.47 Mg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) was also observed in Calabria, Molise, Liguria and Sardinia, regions characterized by the lowest yields (and therefore, low C_{input} by residues). In addition, even where the area of organic agriculture is more than 20% (Calabria, Lazio and Tuscany), there is no reversal of the negative trend but only a slight reduction in SOC losses.

Tab.7: Initial SOC STOCK average values (Mg ha⁻¹) and simulated for different scenarios in the case of the residues management measure, at regional and Italian level, and yearly SOC variation (Mg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹)

Region	SOC STOCK (Mg ha ⁻¹)				Δ SOC/ 20 years (Mg ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)		
	Initial	No	Current	Potential	No	Current	Potential
Abruzzo	57.63	52.55	52.66	52.72	-0.25	-0.25	-0.25
Apulia	47.55	43.41	43.62	43.73	-0.21	-0.20	-0.19
Basilicata	55.17	47.91	48.21	48.74	-0.36	-0.35	-0.32
Calabria	60.20	51.06	51.28	51.41	-0.46	-0.45	-0.44
Campania	61.68	55.53	55.56	55.77	-0.31	-0.31	-0.30
Emilia-Romagna	50.29	51.40	51.59	51.84	0.06	0.06	0.08
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	55.43	55.67	55.69	55.79	0.01	0.01	0.02
Lazio	57.01	50.64	50.88	51.02	-0.32	-0.31	-0.30
Liguria	72.05	62.77	62.76	62.74	-0.46	-0.46	-0.47
Lombardy	46.51	45.53	45.64	45.84	-0.05	-0.04	-0.03
Marche	56.14	51.79	51.99	52.19	-0.22	-0.21	-0.20
Molise	61.04	51.66	51.69	51.72	-0.47	-0.47	-0.47
Piedmont	51.51	52.35	52.50	52.62	0.04	0.05	0.06
Sardinia	58.04	48.11	48.19	48.19	-0.50	-0.49	-0.49
Sicily	57.06	50.02	50.20	50.25	-0.35	-0.34	-0.34
Trentino-Alto Adige	106.40	92.78	93.14	93.16	-0.68	-0.66	-0.66
Tuscany	55.06	51.64	52.01	52.59	-0.17	-0.15	-0.12
Umbria	62.99	61.61	61.81	61.91	-0.07	-0.06	-0.05
Veneto	51.79	58.02	58.08	58.25	0.31	0.31	0.32
Italy	54.65	50.66	50.83	51.00	-0.20	-0.19	-0.18

3.3 Legume fodder crops/ley instead of maize

The simulation of the SOC dynamics for fodder crops partially substituting silage maize outlines an overall increase in SOC levels after 20 years, both in the case of the current and the potential scenario compared to the initial SOC STOCK. There was only one exception, Lombardy, while in Sicily SOC stock value remains almost constant (Tab. 8).

The greater inclusion of autumn-winter cereals and legumes in the potential scenario (2 years of maize and 3 years Cereals+legumes) compared to the current one (3 years of maize and 2 years Cereals+legumes) brings a lower quantity of carbon to the soil because of the lower yield of autumn-winter cereals and legumes compared to maize. Moreover, if maize is more frequently grown on a land, its productivity would very likely decrease over time due to the depletion of soil fertility. To account for these two aspects, the ISTAT yield data for maize in all regions was increased by 13% (<https://www.ilnuovoagricoltore.it/90mila-euro-in-piu-con-medica-e-mais-in-avvicendamento/>), in the potential scenario.

The effect of the increase of organic agriculture areas in 2022 (potential scenario, Tab. 8) compared to the previous PAC (2013, current scenario, Tab. 8) is very small everywhere, even in the regions characterize by more than 20% of organic agriculture area. The greatest increase in SOC stock is observed in Trentino where both maize and legume production are very high, and the most virtuous management becomes particularly successful.

Table.8 Initial SOC STOCK average values (Mg ha^{-1}) and simulated values for different scenarios in the case of the partial substitution of Silage maize with fodder legumes, at regional and Italian level, and yearly SOC variation ($\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)

Region	SOC STOCK Mg ha^{-1}			D SOC/ 20 years ($\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)	
	Initial	Current	Potential	Current	Potential
Abruzzo	57.63	63.78	63.86	0.308	0.312
Apulia	47.55	49.62	49.53	0.103	0.099
Basilicata	55.17	67.05	68.81	0.594	0.682
Calabria	60.20	60.85	61.21	0.032	0.050
Campania	61.68	65.84	65.90	0.208	0.211
Emilia-Romagna	50.29	61.16	61.43	0.544	0.557
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	55.43	60.67	60.75	0.262	0.266
Lazio	57.01	60.94	60.96	0.197	0.198
Liguria	72.05	80.49	80.86	0.422	0.441
Lombardy	46.51	42.40	43.43	-0.206	-0.154
Marche	56.14	60.12	60.40	0.199	0.213
Molise	61.04	66.45	66.54	0.271	0.275
Piemonte	51.51	58.07	58.11	0.328	0.330
Sardinia	58.04	68.07	68.52	0.501	0.524
Sicily	57.06	55.75	56.40	-0.066	-0.033
Trentino-Alto Adige	106.40	138.88	140.50	1.624	1.705
Tuscany	55.06	58.92	59.03	0.193	0.198
Umbria	62.99	63.47	63.73	0.024	0.037
Veneto	51.79	61.62	61.71	0.492	0.496
Italy	54.65	59.08	59.43	0.22	0.24

4. Conclusions

This report illustrates a comparative analysis about the efficacy of different agricultural measures (cover crops, residues management and use of legume fodder crops instead of maize) with respect to SOC sequestration potential, at Italian level, for several scenarios by simulating the SOC STOCK dynamics over 20 years. Starting from the INSPIRE pedological grid (10 km x 10 km) database, along with AGRIC4CAST climate data, and both AGRIT and ISTAT information about crop surface areas and yields, SOC STOCK simulations were carried out for each Italian region with the RothC10_N model.

Considering that the simulated agricultural measures are all part of the organic farming system, the definition of the “current” and “potential” scenarios was tied to the organic agriculture area surveyed in Italy, respectively in 2013 and 2022. These years were chosen because they are the last years of the 2007-2013 and 2014 – 2022 CAP programming period, the second being more ambitious in terms of organic farming targets and therefore considered as a potential scenario. This approach aimed at estimating SOC sequestration potentials in realistic scenarios.

The reported results may often appear pessimistic and almost far from reality, and this might be due to the fact that the measures were simulated separately.

For instance, the introduction of cover crops alone is not even effective even in maintaining the initial SOC STOCK content.

The simulation of crops residues management seems to be more in line with reality, in fact it shows very varied results between the regions depending, above all, on the respective crop yields. In addition, the simulation was made on a rotation that included autumn-winter cereals. Provided that the nearly half of the arable land in Italy is cultivated with cereals, the simulations on SOC dynamics are more truthful, in the sense that the initial SOC value described in the INSPIRE grid might describe an agricultural context very similar to the simulated one and at the equilibrium.

With regard to the use of legume fodder crops instead of maize, this is the only measure that showed an overall increase of SOC STOCK content over 20 years, regardless of the fodder legume crop adopted in the rotation. This might be explained by the fact that maize releases in the soil a greater amount of carbon from the roots (Ngidi et al., 2024). Therefore, even if the simulation didn't include the C_{input} from crop residues, the carbon entry for the soil is conspicuous. When legumes fodder crops are included in the rotation with a higher frequency, at the expense of maize, a reduction of C_{input} was observed, due to the lower yields of leguminous crops. However, to account for the improvement in soil fertility as a consequence of the introduction of legumes, an increase in maize yield by 13%, according to literature, was imposed. This guaranteed a positive trend in SOC STOCK in the potential scenario, compared to the current one.

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